

Generalized n^{th} order derivative formula

Zain Ul Abideen
SS09, IST.
jvlian.assange@gmail.com

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1 Abstract

The n^{th} order derivative formula was derived by exploiting the pattern of binomial coefficients that appear when expanding the higher order definitions of derivatives. The final unified form was obtained by a lot of trial and error as it will be evident in the paper.

2 Formulation

let $f(x)$ be a function which is continuous and differentiable on all its domain. By the definition of derivative:

$$\frac{df(x)}{dx} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x+h) - f(x)}{h} \quad (1)$$

Similarly, for higher order derivatives, we can use the definition multiple times:

$$\frac{d^2f}{dx^2} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x+2h) - 2f(x+h) + f(x)}{h^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{d^3f}{dx^3} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x+3h) - 3f(x+2h) + 3f(x+h) - f(x)}{h^3} \quad (3)$$

and so on.

Having a closer look at the coefficients revealed a pattern. These are the same coefficients that appear in the binomial expansion of $(a+b)^n$. The binomial theorem states:

$$(a+b)^n = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (a)^{n-k} (b)^k \quad (4)$$

Now enough information was available to start the process of formulation. First thing to be decided was that $\binom{n}{c}$ had to be there in the formula to cover for the coefficients. The second thing would be to make use of a finite sum \sum to have the coefficients of h iterated in the argument of the function f . The final thing would be the need to raise (-1) to some iterating power to account for the alternating negative signs with the binomial coefficients. After alot of trial and error, the following formulae were derived:

for $n \in \{\text{positive odd numbers}\}$:

$$\frac{d^n f}{dx^n} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{c} \frac{f(x + kh)(-1)^{k+1}}{h^n} \quad (5)$$

for $n \in \{\text{positive even numbers including zero}\}$:

$$\frac{d^n f}{dx^n} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{c} \frac{f(x + kh)(-1)^k}{h^n} \quad (6)$$

Further analysis showed that both of these formulae could be unified into a single formula valid for all natural numbers:

for $n \in \mathbf{N}$:

$$\frac{d^n f}{dx^n} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{c} \frac{f(x + kh)(-1)^{k+n}}{h^n} \quad (7)$$

The above formula does not work for fractional derivatives, only for positive integers. This results from the fact that $\binom{n}{c}$ is undefined for negative and fractional values.

3 Examples

3.1 first example

Evaluating the third derivative of e^{2x} results in the following expression:

$$\frac{d^3 f}{dx^3} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \sum_{k=0}^3 \binom{3}{k} \left[\frac{f(x + kh)(-1)^{k+3}}{h^3} \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^3 f}{dx^3} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} & \left[\frac{f(x) \times (1)(-1)^{0+3}}{h^3} + \frac{f(x+h) \times (3)(-1)^{1+3}}{h^3} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{f(x+2h) \times (3)(-1)^{2+3}}{h^3} + \frac{f(x+3h) \times (1)(-1)^{3+3}}{h^3} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{d^3 f}{dx^3} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{e^{2(x+3h)} - 3e^{2(x+2h)} + 3e^{2(x+h)} - e^{2x}}{h^3} \right]$$

$$\frac{d^3 f}{dx^3} = e^{2x} \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{e^{6h} - 3e^{4h} + 3e^{2h} - 1}{h^3} \right]$$

The limit computationally converges to 8.

$$\frac{d^3 f}{dx^3} = 8e^{2x}$$

Which is indeed the correct result.

3.2 second example

Evaluating the fourth derivative of $\sin(x)$ results in the following expression:

$$\frac{d^4 f}{dx^4} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \sum_{k=0}^4 \binom{4}{k} \left[\frac{f(x+kh)(-1)^{k+4}}{h^4} \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^4 f}{dx^4} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} & \left[\frac{f(x) \times (1)(-1)^{0+4}}{h^4} + \frac{f(x+h) \times (4)(-1)^{1+4}}{h^4} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{f(x+2h) \times (6)(-1)^{2+4}}{h^4} + \frac{f(x+3h) \times (4)(-1)^{3+4}}{h^4} + \frac{f(x+4h) \times (1)(-1)^{4+4}}{h^4} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{d^4 f}{dx^4} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\sin(x) - 4\sin(x+h) + 6\sin(x+2h) - 4\sin(x+3h) + \sin(x+4h)}{h^4} \right]$$

Expanding using the trigonometric sum identities.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^4 f}{dx^4} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} & \left[\sin(x) \frac{1 - 4\cos(h) + 6\cos(2h) - 4\cos(3h) + \cos(4h)}{h^4} \right] \\ & + \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \left[\cos(x) \frac{-4\sin(h) + 6\sin(2h) - 4\sin(3h) + \sin(4h)}{h^4} \right] \end{aligned}$$

The limits computationally converge to 1 and 0 respectively.

$$\frac{d^4 f}{dx^4} = \sin(x)(1) + \cos(x)(0) = \sin(x)$$

Which is indeed the correct result.

4 Works Used

- [1] Thomas, George Brinton, et al. Thomas' calculus. Addison-Wesley, 2005.